

MANUAL FOR A RAPID QUALITATIVE INQUIRY OF CONTEXT

Supporting the implementation of Group Care in your local context

Authors: Matty Crone, Nele Martens, Ria Reis

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Section 1: Introduction

The purpose of this document

This document serves as a guideline on how to understand and analyse the context in which Group Care will be implemented in your country, using Rapid Qualitative Inquiry (RQI). RQI is an efficient, team-based approach to collect and analyse qualitative data (Beebe 2014). In complex situations the insider (emic) and outsider (etic) perspectives can be insightful and this is what RQI researchers set out to do.

How to conduct a context analysis

The implementation of Evidence Based Interventions (EBI) in new settings does not always translate into improved health outcomes of recipients. Contextual factors are at the root of such implementation failures. This is why a sound understanding of your context is so important (Bauer and Kirchner 2020). The concept of “context” encompasses more than merely the implementation setting. Context is the multi-layered set of dynamic characteristics and circumstances influencing implementation (Martens et al. 2022). Hence, context is a broad and complex concept and the idea of assessing the context might feel overwhelming at the beginning of a project. We applied the Basel Approach for coNtextual ANALysis (BANANA) to assist as a framework for understanding what we needed to study, BANANA was developed to provide guidance for the assessment of context (Mielke et al. 2019). It entails six steps, which are elaborated on in section 2.

FURTHER READING

Mielke, J., et al. The Basel Approach for coNtextual ANALysis (BANANA) in Implementation Science Using the SMILe Project as an Example. Presentation at: ESPACOMP (2019).

Before applying BANANA it is important to first formulate your research question:

This is a first step to reflect on what it is you want to know about your context before introducing Group Care.

You may be interested in specific factors related to the implementation setting (e.g., the clinical practice, or hospital). In that case your research questions could be similar to the two example questions below:

- What is the *implementation climate* at the implementation setting and how might it affect Group Care implementation?
- Is there a *readiness for change* at the implementation setting?

However, you may also opt for a broad focus, in which case, your research question will include factors related to the implementation setting and beyond. For example:

- Which factors in the social, political or economic environment in your country may affect the implementation of a new model of antenatal and/or postnatal care?

The focus of your research question depends on what contextual factors are important in your setting, the availability of information from previous research and the availability of resources to conduct further research. If Group Care has already been implemented in your country/district, evidence on relevant implementation determinants may already be available, allowing you to focus on selected factors (please look for literature on your local context). However, if little is known about the implementation of Group Care in your country/district, you will first need to start with understanding the country and organisational context within which you will implement Group Care. It is also important to keep your resources for research in mind when formulating your research question.

Section 2: Applying the Basel Approach for contextual ANALYSIS (BANANA)

2.1 Identify a theory or framework that will help to guide your data collection and analysis of key features of context

Using a theoretical framework can aid in understanding important contextual factors that you would like to implement Group Care. It helps to systematically look at the potential domains and factors that can influence implementation. Based on our experience in the GC-1000- implementation research project, we suggest using the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR) to identify key domains you would like to explore in the context and as a tool for analysis of context (Damschroder 2009, 2022). The CFIR describes five domains that are crucial for study, with each domain consisting of constructs that impact the implementation of Group Care.

In Section 1.1, we briefly list the content of each CFIR domain. These domains are interconnected rather than distinct, and their inter-relationships, along with detailed definitions, can be visually explored in the work of Damschroder (2009, 2022). To illustrate the practical application of these domains, we provide empirical examples from the GC-1000 implementation research project in Table 6.

FURTHER READING

Damschroder, L.J., et al. Fostering implementation of health services research findings into practice: a consolidated framework for advancing implementation science. *Implementation Science* 4, 50 (2009).

Damschroder, L.J., Reardon, C.M., Widerquist, M.A.O. & Lowery, J. The updated Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research based on user feedback. *Implementation Science* 17, 1-16 (2022).

The domains of the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR)

Domain 1: The innovation is an intervention or model being implemented, and it is typically new to those implementing it. In the GC-1000 project, the innovation was the Group Care model. *“The first major domain of the CFIR is related to characteristics of the intervention being implemented into a particular organization”* (Damschroder et al, 2009, p. 4)

Table 1: Constructs within the innovation domain

Intervention source
● Evidence-base
● Relative advantage
● Adaptability
● Trialability
● Complexity
● Design
● Cost

Domain 2: The outer setting is the multi-level setting in which the inner setting is embedded.

The outer setting is the multi-level setting in which the inner setting is embedded. This includes the economic, social, and political context with an organisation (Damschroder et al. 2009:).

Table 2: Constructs within the outer setting

● Critical incidents
● Values and beliefs
● Systemic conditions
● Policies and laws
● Partnerships and connections
● Financing
● External pressure

Domain 3: The inner setting is the implementation setting (such as a midwifery practice or hospital) where Group Care will be implemented. It is influenced by what is happening in the outer setting, such as national policies affecting how midwives are paid for their services. *“The inner setting may be composed of tightly or loosely coupled entities (e.g., a loosely affiliated medical center and outlying contracted clinics or tightly integrated service lines within a health system)”* (Damschroder et al. 2009:5).

TOOL

To help you identify important inner setting factors, you can use the Group Care Global Readiness Assessment tool for antenatal (Appendix 1) and postnatal care (Appendix 2).

Table 3: Constructs within the inner setting

Domain 4: Refers to the roles and characteristics of individuals involved in the inner and outer setting (e.g., midwives, doctors, policy makers, families, community leaders).

Table 4: Constructs in the domain of individual characteristics

We have not included the process domain here, as the contextual analysis is completed before implementation begins.

2.2 Use empirical evidence to identify Group Care specific implementation determinants

Within the GC_1000 research project, we studied diverse implementation settings to identify contextual factors (barriers and facilitators) that tend to impact the implementation of Group Care. An overview is provided below in Table 6 to serve as examples of what could be found in context.

Table 6: Using empirical evidence to identify Group Care specific implementation determinants

CFIR construct	Sub-construct	Context and findings on implementation
INTERVENTION CHARACTERISTICS	Evidence strength & quality	Systematic review evidence exists of benefits for more underserved and disadvantaged communities; engagement and satisfaction with care and provider satisfaction (Byerley & Haas 2017); however, participants understood the evidence more fully through participation in the workshops, supported by programme materials and meetings and by the experience of facilitating group care and feedback from participants.
	Intervention source	Engagement and involvement with a range of stakeholders was built in and experienced as vital throughout. GC_1000 country teams had local and national networks & credibility. Final stakeholder workshops including range of actors was recognised as important for sustainability post-programme
	Relative advantage	Stakeholders perceived benefits especially for more underserved populations, but some had reservations about acceptability and costs compared with individual care
	Adaptability	Programme built in RQI and adaptations packages to ensure sensitivity to context; some planned and unplanned adaptations made without major impact on fidelity of the model;
	Triability	Antenatal and in some countries ante- and postnatal groups were piloted on a small scale in each country depending on previous experience with group care and context challenges. Small-scale pilot seen in some settings as vital to test local feasibility and impact but had implications for costs of care. Evaluation was built into programme structure and each phase of work.
	Complexity	Implementation was complex, requiring training, planning with a range of stakeholders, financial and staffing arrangements, obtaining venues, materials and handbooks.
	Design quality & packaging	Development of modules, handbooks and attractive information materials for service providers and users was important to support implementation. Trainers provided follow-up mentoring
	Cost	Costs of the time for training and planning were potential barriers in resource constrained health systems in high as well as low-middle income countries. Costs of implementation per se were significant and could be challenging without external support or transitional funding; Costs of time for group sessions lasting 2 hours were a major factor, particularly when services had difficulties in recruiting and retaining 8-12 participants. Many groups were smaller for reasons including impact of Covid-19, recruitment challenges rooted in unfamiliarity of the model, discomfort with the group setting and concerns about time to attend longer sessions, loss due to miscarriages and population mobility and rural settings with smaller maternity population.

CFIR construct	Sub-construct	Context and findings on implementation
OUTER SETTING	Patient needs & resources	Groups were targeted where feasible to more underserved socio-economically disadvantaged communities, where care uptake is lower and maternity outcomes often poorer
	Cosmopolitanism & peer pressure	The partner organisations in each country drew on their networks to engage services; the services involved were typically those with higher readiness and external connections, so engagement work needed for scale-up.
	External policy and incentives	<p>WHO policy advocates in context of evaluation but most countries did not have policies specifically to support this model. Health system structure and funding models typically formed barriers to implementation despite broader policy motivations to improve uptake, equity and outcomes of care and to enhance respectful care, mental health and public health.</p> <p>Health systems in the seven countries varied between universal, social insurance and public/private mix. Lack of midwife-led care or scope and autonomy of midwifery in some countries posed financial and system barriers to implementation because of limited status, roles in decision-making, and in some settings (Belgium, Suriname and in some settings in Kosovo) duplication of maternity care with gynaecologists or family doctors.</p> <p>While health policy in several countries (e.g. Suriname, UK, South Africa) advocates more preventive and public health care, resources remain typically focused on secondary/curative care.</p>
INNER SETTING	Structural characteristics	Maternity service configurations varied widely with some more hospital-centred and others more community centred; rural settings had challenges of patients' numbers and clinic accessibility; most had challenges relating to boundaries between different services or parts of services, such as hospital and community care settings, or health services versus municipalities. In Netherlands and Belgium midwifery practices had more independence but experienced challenges in integration with wider services. While in Belgium, lack of establishment of midwife led antenatal care was a barrier, the more autonomous professional role of midwives in the Netherlands and the UK, with midwife-led care for low-risk women was a facilitator.
	Networks and communications	Communication and integration between different parts of a service were important but sometimes challenging – in some cases led to duplication of visit schedules, inappropriate rostering of midwives which undermined continuity.
	Culture, implementation climate & tension for change	Services were in effect 'demonstration sites' with a higher level of interest in and readiness for change; some were characterised by strong leadership and motivated professionals. The hospital in South Africa, for example, was 'mother-baby friendly' and midwives received positive leadership support; the hospital was observed to be a welcoming environment with positive and respectful messages for patients; for scale-up their experience needs to be translated positively to a wider range of services.

CFIR construct	Sub-construct	Context and findings on implementation
	Compatibility	As small-scale pilots, group facilitators were typically volunteers aligned with group care values, open to change, motivated to enhance service engagement, equity and outcomes; nonetheless, they and those with more reservations found reinforcement through the experience of the role modelling in training workshops and the experience of group facilitation, with programme and local leadership support. Some undertook 'train the trainer' courses provided in some settings (UK, Ghana, Suriname Kosovo and Netherlands) to help with future spread and sustainability. Sharing experience with other professionals was encouraged.
	Relative priority	Implementation in the programme tended to occur in the organizations where leaders recognised the potential benefits and promoted the concept.
	Organisational incentives and rewards	Potential incentives for facilitators could include working with more autonomy; most commented on the professional satisfaction and enjoyment of working this way. In Kosovo and Suriname, midwives wanted economic incentives to provide group care as it was perceived as additional to their usual work; in both contexts midwives felt their roles were not sufficiently recognised and they lacked autonomy and power in the services; duplication of visits by gynaecologists was a financial challenge, as funding for midwifery care was less likely to be prioritised in health system expenditure.
	Goals & feedback	The support and evaluation built into the GC_1000 programme would need to be replicated in local systems to support scale-up and sustainability.
	Learning climate	Organisations with an open and positive learning climate were more likely to be engaged in a programme of this type; nonetheless, aspects of the implementation (training, reflections, mentoring & evaluation) were reinforced by the model itself, which is focused on active and interactive learning.
	Readiness for implementation	Even those services with more readiness for involvement commented on the value of training and provision of materials and handbooks and other forms of support to begin implementation. Train-the-trainer workshops were important for sustainability by cascading the relevant knowledge so that organisations could continue to scale-up with the external training support of the GC_1000 programme. Training would need to be integrated into regular professional education in future.
	Leadership engagement	Commitment, involvement and engagement of leaders was reinforced by setting up steering groups and convening stakeholder meetings.
	Available resources	The GC_1000 programme provided in-kind resources to support initial implementation. Key local challenges included lack of rooms large enough for groups, lack of free access to suitable community-based venues, lack of budgets for snacks or to buy materials. Staffing shortages and lack of time to free professionals for training and for facilitation of the groups was a widespread concern and a major challenge in high and lower-middle income countries.

CFIR construct	Sub-construct	Context and findings on implementation
	Access to knowledge and information	The information and support provided by the programme would need to be replicated in services for scale up, including relevant clinical guidelines and clinic schedules, summaries of supporting evidence, skills to provide the training workshops (train-the-trainers sessions and midwife handbooks were provided in several countries to support this). Group Care Global modules were developed and all resources to be fed into GC_1000 toolkit.
CHARACTERISTICS OF INDIVIDUALS	Knowledge and beliefs about the intervention	Although professionals who volunteered were more likely to be open to the intervention the style of the training was observed to be a key component in professionals and managers understanding of group care principles and potential benefits, for providers as well as for patients. Experience reinforced interest and was found to allay concerns of some professionals who had more reservations about the value. Professional or manager reservations, noted for some in all countries, included concerns about: lack of privacy, limited 1-2-1 time, reluctance to include women with risk factors or to facilitate diverse groups, worries about more patient-led discussion and the accuracy of self-assessments
	Self-efficacy & individual stage of change; personal attributes	Some professionals also shared their personal lack of confidence in group facilitation, that they would be too introverted or unable to manage any difficult group dynamics or would not know how to deal with 'wrong' information shared by parents. The style of the training workshops helped to address fears and provided opportunities to practice skills; most were observed to grow in skills and confidence over time but constrained resources in some settings limited take-up of mentoring and reflection sessions; midwives in some settings (e.g. South Africa) spoke about learning from the groups, they saw the group as a co-learning space. Women participants, and where relevant their partners, talked about gaining in confidence through the interactive discussion and their involvement in health checks. Not all professionals initially welcomed the learning style, but interviews and survey responses highlighted that most found it rewarding and enjoyable in practice.
	Patient/client circumstances	In high as well as lower-income countries, with high levels of disparity, lack of time and personal resources could deter take-up of longer visits. Not all parents would receive maternity benefits such as paid leave for care, support for childcare or ability to bring food to share.
PROCESS	Planning	Planning for implementation involved identification and analysis of contextual challenges and opportunities (RQ1) and then supported by WP4. Training workshops and modules, development of support materials were a key aspect. Considerable time was spent by providers in identifying suitable venues and resources.
	Engaging	Engagement with decision-makers and communities was an important aspect and included in some settings inclusion in training workshops. Continuing engagement via steering groups and later workshops with stakeholders was important to maintain engagement.
	Opinion leaders	Identifying and supporting local champions was key to progress.

CFIR construct	Sub-construct	Context and findings on implementation
	Formally appointed implementation leaders	GC_1000 teams were key actors initially but sought to transfer leadership to local service personnel. Eg., in the UK, consultant midwives acted as lead investigator for each site. In South Africa the manager of the outpatient ANC clinic within the maternity hospital was nominated as the implementation lead in the hospital given this was her area of oversight in the hospital. She needed to report on progress to those higher up in the bureaucracy, the nursing manager was her immediate line manager.
	Champions	The midwife-facilitator in the hospital in South Africa was a champion for the model, supported recruitment of women, manually scheduled women into groups as current scheduling systems is not set up this way, spoke to her colleagues in other departments in the hospital and provided regular insight on what she enjoyed most about the model to others in the hospital. She also completed Master training in the hopes of training others in the hospital to facilitate more groups. One concern though, is that her manager is worried about burn out due to all the time she invests in Group Care.
	External change agents	The GC_1000 consortium partners acted as key external change agents but sought to involve relevant health and social care and community-based organisations that could continue to support implementation after the programme.
	Executing	The programme structure with regular country and work-package lead meetings provided a structure and momentum for implementation.
	Reflecting & evaluating	Regular GC_1000 meetings were complemented with local steering group or national advisory group meetings, with review and reflection on progress. Group care trainers provided follow-up mentoring for facilitators and offered reflection sessions. Evaluation was conducted alongside implementation, but facilitators were also encouraged to evaluate their own work.

2.3 Involve Stakeholders

If Group Care is new in your region, it can be useful to involve people outside your organisation to raise awareness, create acceptability amongst women/families, ease recruitment and to lobby for the recognition of Group Care in the health care system. External stakeholders may include influential community members or leaders, such as village heads, priests, football coaches and policy makers.

2.4 Develop a feasible study design for context analysis: Using Rapid Qualitative Inquiry (RQI)

Your study design and data collection procedures are dependent on the contextual factors you decide to focus on and therefore, ultimately on your research questions. When your main interest lies in assessing a few specific contextual factors such as *implementation climate or readiness for change*, you can make use of existing questionnaires (see [CFIR website](#)). However, when you have less understanding of what might be important for the implementation of Group Care, including multiple or all CFIR domains, a qualitative or mixed methods design is more appropriate. Qualitative methods that you could make use of include interviews, focus groups and/or observations. Mixed methods refer to a combination of such qualitative methods and questionnaires.

DEFINITION

RQI is an efficient, team-based approach for collecting and analysing qualitative data. It uses readily available information from sources such as government, academia, and local organisations).

RQI is based on four core principles:

1. An inductive and iterative approach allows themes to emerge from empirical data and informs subsequent data collection steps (e.g. identifying new informants, adjusting topic lists). This approach also supports practical implementation.
2. Data is collected from observations, key informant interviews, semi-structured interviews with purposely selected local informants, and literature. This data will be triangulated to ensure scientific rigour and validity.
3. The focus is on the emic perspectives (inside, subjective views) of women, parents, professionals, and policymakers.
4. Local ownership will be ensured by involving professionals, women, and parents as co-researchers from the beginning of the research process

When conducting an RQI, it is important to gather a multidisciplinary team of 'researchers', usually a combination of professionals and lay researchers (e.g., midwives, doctors, pregnant or parenting people). This team should include both insiders and outsiders. Insiders have in-depth, first-hand knowledge of antenatal and/or postnatal care, including the relevant culture and policies. For example, pregnant or parenting people or a midwife or paediatrician from the local area would be considered as an insider, whereas an academic researcher or a doctor from a different area would be an outsider.

For RQI data collection, it is important to engage not only key decision-makers (outer setting) but also **local** health care professionals and patients (inner setting).

Next, make a list of participant categories (e.g., midwife, pregnant or parenting people, hospital manager) for your interviews and/or focus groups. In the Appendices, we provide research tools that you can use for interviewing key stakeholders, such as women and health care professionals.

TOOLS FOR CONDUCTING RESEARCH

See the Appendices section for interview guides:

- Appendix 3: Topic guide for healthcare providers
- Appendix 4: Topic guide for women who have experience with Group Care
- Appendix 5: Topic guide for women who have no experience with Group Care
- Appendix 6: Topic guide for partner organisations from your setting

We also provide a vignette (story) that can be used to introduce Group Care to interviewees who are not familiar with Group Care (see Appendix 7).

We suggest using contact summary forms to note the most relevant information after each data collection activity as they will be helpful during the team debriefings (see Appendix 8).

It is important that you **adapt** these tools to match your context and research question. Involve your **insider researchers** to help you adapt and consider research tool adaptation as an iterative process; interview guides are not static but they can be adapted at any time.

Once your research tools are ready and have been piloted, identify participants, and gather their contact details. Thorough planning is pivotal for RQI, so it's advisable to schedule all data collection activities in advance and delegate responsibilities and tasks (e.g., who will recruit participants). As a researcher, you should be familiar about the background of your interviewee, and you need to know **why** this person is being interviewed. This knowledge allows you to tailor your questions to each interviewee's expertise. The research team will collect qualitative data (interviews, focus groups and observation data) over a period of 1-2 weeks, aiming to understand both insider and outsider perspectives. During the research period, the team will meet daily at the end of the day to discuss their findings, identify remaining questions, plan how to gather missing information, and collaboratively analyse the findings.

what they have learned, what questions remain unanswered, how to gather information that is still lacking, and to analyse their findings collaboratively. These daily debriefings are also an opportunity to critically reflect on and amend your research tools, if needed.

2.5 Identifying and describing the relevance of contextual and setting factors for intervention co-design, implementation strategies, and outcomes

During debriefing sessions, all researchers discuss what they learned and to what extent the research question was answered. In this way, contextual factors are identified in a collaborative effort. Adaptations and implementation strategies that need to be tailored to the contextual factors you have found, should also be discussed during daily debriefings. The RQI ends with a final

debriefing where (co-)researchers discuss the main barriers and facilitators to implementation and they will agree on strategies to handle these factors.

2.6 Reporting of contextual analysis

Reporting and publishing your findings can help expand the knowledge of contextual factors relevant to the implementation of Group Care. In the section below, we provide examples of contextual factors that influenced the implementation of Group Care in the seven countries in the GC-1000 project which can be found [here on this linked website](#).

Example 6.1

CASE STUDY FROM SURINAME

Concerns regarding trust and privacy in Group Care were not only reiterated across respondent groups in this study but they were also identified in multiple previous studies. The tightly-knit communities in the suburbs of the districts, Paramaribo and Wanica, appear to act as catalysts for such apprehensions.

LESSON

Settings with similar social structures should be alert as they may encounter similarly accelerated concerns around privacy. Another study identified five prerequisites to building trust in Group Care (vulnerability, communication, reciprocity, chemistry and atmosphere), and emphasised that the development of trust needs time (Kweekel et al. 2017). Hence, when recruiting pregnant or parenting people for Group Care – before they have met other group members – it may not suffice to openly discuss privacy and confidentiality-related issues, but the use of a confidentiality agreement may help overcome concerns at a time when trust has not yet had time to develop.

Example 6.2:

CASE STUDY FROM THE NETHERLANDS

Confidence existed amongst most respondents with regard to their communication skills, sensitivity, and adaptability. Nevertheless, Health Care Providers (HCPs) stated that additional skills, such as the ability to guide group discussions, manage dynamics, and foster a respectful environment are prerequisites to becoming a competent facilitator. Dutch midwives raised concerns about their personal competence to “shift gears mentally” from individual to Group Care. Two Dutch midwives, specifically stressed that they were nervous about being in front of a group of people. Furthermore, the majority of Dutch midwives doubted their competency to effectively manage the time allocated for the three-minute individual assessment, while also addressing the emotional needs of the women. However, HCPs with previous Group Care experience appeared to be more self-confident and have increased trust in Group Care’s methods and eagerness towards its implementation.

LESSON:

Self-efficacy and motivation to implement are intertwined. Providing the Group Care training can increase self-confidence and motivation.

Example 6.3

CASE STUDY FROM SOUTH AFRICA

In the Provincial Government, where Group Care was supposed to be implemented, the Provincial Department of Health already had a clear vision for the first 1000 days of life, and they were keen to learn more about ways in which new interventions could support the goals in this area. When conducting the context analysis, this provided an opportunity to share information with them. Thus, their existing vision, provided a basis for support for the implementation research at the Provincial level from key stakeholders.

LESSON:

Identify policy actors who share the values of a Group Care approach and/or find policies in your country that align well with the vision of Group Care – this will enable you to show how Group Care can contribute to goals that already exist.

REFERENCES:

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2. Bauer, M.S & Kirchner, J. Implementation science: What is it and why should I care? *Psychiatry research* **283**, 112376 (2020).
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APPENDICES:

APPENDIX 1: Group Care Global Site Readiness Assessment (SRA) for implementation of Group Care (Antenatal)

Completing this form will help you to determine the readiness of your clinical site to implement group *antenatal* care.

Please complete a separate form for each site.

Date completed (Day/Month/Year)
Completed by
Title

COUNTRY:

SITE NAME:

Please mark the number that best indicates the readiness of the site, according to each category

Administrative Support	
	None or unknown
	Beginning support Key administrator(s) have been contacted about plans to begin work on possible model implementation and indicated initial support/interest

	<p>Fully supportive; part of planning</p> <p>Key administrator(s) supportive of moving forward with implementation work and are part of the planning team</p>
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Clinical Staff Involvement	
	None or unknown
	<p>Early involvement in planning</p> <p>Key clinicians interested in participating in the model project. Beginning information reviewed on the model</p>
	<p>Champion involved</p> <p>Familiarity with group care models. There are key providers, including midwives and physicians, actively involved in the planning</p>

Population Served	
	Not identified or fewer than 15 pregnant women of similar gestational age available per month to make a cohort
	<p>Between 15-30 women available per month to make a cohort</p> <p>Some data regarding general risk factors, suitability for group care</p>
	<p>30+ women available per month to make a cohort</p> <p>Numbers available on antenatal registrants/month, assurance that there are enough women to easily make <i>monthly</i> cohorts of 10-12 women with similar gestation</p>

Space for Groups	
	No identified appropriate space
	<p>Access to appropriate space</p> <p>The space available is private and will hold at least 20 chairs/pillows in an open circle. Recommended: at least 20 ft x20 ft / 6m x 6m; square is better than rectangular</p>
	<p>Dedicated appropriate space available</p> <p>All of the above (#1) but space is dedicated to the group implementation so doesn't need to be set up/rearranged for every group. In general, it is better to have a space that is too big rather than one that is on the small side</p>

Funding for Group Care	
	None identified
	In-kind funding available to support group needs
	Internal or ongoing grant funding available for sustaining the model after the grant ends

Evaluation of Group Care	
	No data available or accessible for evaluation
	Data collection taking place at the site Site has a process for collecting basic data on patients including baselines, such as registration for care and attendance
	Site committed to data collection and evaluation Besides basic data collection there is evaluation of health outcomes based on site benchmarking

Language: Steering Committee for work with Group Care Global (GCG)	
	Limited facility with English
	Some comfort with English
	Most committee members have facility with English

Language: Group Participant cohort formation	
	Forming group cohorts difficult due to multiple language challenges
	Separate groups based on language needed for communication Education materials available in a variety of languages
	Language not an issue for placement in groups Education materials available

Other assessment items for comment:

Site Self-Assessment:

Notes from discussion with GCG:

APPENDIX 2: Group Care Global Site Readiness Assessment (SRA) for implementation of Group Care (Postnatal)

Completing this form will help you to determine the readiness of your clinical site to implement group *postnatal* care.

Please complete a separate form for each site.

Date completed (Day/Month/Year)
Completed by
Title

COUNTRY:

SITE NAME:

Please mark the number that best indicates the readiness of the site, according to each category

Administrative Support	
	None or unknown
	Beginning support Key administrator(s) have been contacted about plans to begin work on possible model implementation and indicated initial support/interest
	Fully supportive; part of planning Key administrator(s) supportive of moving forward with implementation work and are part of the planning team

Clinical Staff Involvement	
	None or unknown
	Early involvement in planning Key clinicians interested in participating in the model project. Beginning information reviewed on the model and/or have experience with antenatal groups
	Champion involved Familiarity with group care models. There are key providers, including midwives and physicians, actively involved in the planning

Population Served	
	Fewer than 6 mothers/babies of similar gestation to form a cohort
	More than 6 mothers/babies of similar gestation to form a cohort
	Antenatal groups active, with ability to transition into postnatal groups

Space for Groups	
	No identified appropriate space
	Access to appropriate space The space available is private and safe for babies to crawl. Room for at least 15 pillows on the floor in a circle. Recommended: at least 20 ft x20 ft / 6m x 6m; square is better than rectangular.
	Dedicated appropriate space available All of the above (#1) but space is dedicated to the group implementation so doesn't need to be set up/rearranged for every group. In general, it is better to have a space that is too big rather than one that is on the small side

Funding for Group Care	
	None identified
	In-kind funding available to support group needs
	Internal or ongoing grant funding available for sustaining the model after the grant ends

Evaluation of Group Care	
	No data available or accessible for evaluation
	Data collection taking place at the site Site has a process for collecting basic data on patients including baselines, such as registration for care and attendance

	<p>Site committed to data collection and evaluation</p> <p>Besides basic data collection there is evaluation of health outcomes based on site benchmarking</p>
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Language: Steering Committee for work with Group Care Global (GCG)	
	Limited facility with English
	Some comfort with English
	Most committee members have facility with English

Language: Group Participant cohort formation	
	Forming group cohorts difficult due to multiple language challenges
	<p>Separate groups based on language needed for communication</p> <p>Education materials available in a variety of languages</p>
	<p>Language not an issue for placement in groups</p> <p>Education materials available</p>

Other assessment items for comment:

Site Self-Assessment:

Notes from discussion with GCG:

APPENDIX 3: Topic guide for Healthcare Providers – Antenatal and Postnatal Group Care

Topic	Questions
Start Questions	<p>What is your professional background?</p> <p>What is your role within the organization?</p>
Current model of care & perception thereof	<p>Can you describe the ANC trajectory for a pregnant woman?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Who provides antenatal care? Whom does she meet? ● How many appointments? ● How much time do you spend per consultation? <p>What aspects of ANC do you like/dislike?</p>
Needs of women and babies	<p>Can you describe your patient population? Who will be recruited for the groups?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SES, Ethnicity, Age <p>Can you describe typical challenges of those pregnant women?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Medical issues (HIV, family planning...) ● Practical (transport, financing...) ● Psycho-social (support...) ● Culture-specific (language, etc.)
Perception of GC	<p>What do you already know about GC?</p> <p>Please use the Vignette here if needed (Appendix 7)</p> <p>What do you like/dislike about GC?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Advantages/disadvantages for: you, the organization, women? ● Compared to the current antenatal care? ● Interactive learning methods, such as throwing a ball, introducing the person sitting next to you, self-assessment

<p>Personal involvement and motivation to implement GC</p>	<p>What is your role within the implementation of GC?</p> <p>How did you get involved in the implementation of GC?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Did you decide it yourself? Why? Did someone ask you? ● What motivates you? <p>How was the decision made to implement Group Care in your setting?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Who participated in the decision-making process? ● What were the reasons for this decision? ● How was the decision communicated to you? <p>How will GC affect you?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● working situation/Professional development/career? Work/life balance?
<p>Implementation process/ planning</p>	<p>Can you describe the plan for implementing Group Care within your setting?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How detailed is it? Who knows about it? ● How will Group Care be integrated into the current organization of antenatal care in your setting? Will the intervention replace or complement a current program or process? ● How will women be recruited to participate in the Group Care? ● How will it be possible in times of COVID? Is blended care an option?
<p>Implementation barriers/ facilitators - adaptations</p>	<p>In your view, how can successful implementation be ensured? What to you need?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Changes to the GC model? ● Changes to the organization? ● Who needs to be onboard? ● Changes in health care system ● In times of COVID <p>What might hinder the implementation of GC?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Policies: local/national regulations or guidelines (e.g., reimbursement) ● General health care system in your country ● Socio-cultural factors ● Competing projects ● Staff?

<p>Self-efficacy</p>	<p>What will be challenging for you as a facilitator?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Recruitment ● Leading group discussion ● Certain topics <p>What do you need to resolve those challenges?</p>
<p>Inner setting: organizational structure</p>	<p>Can you describe the working climate in this organization?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Relationship with colleagues and leaders ● Motivation of staff <p>Can you describe the values/priorities of your organization?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hierarchical, entrepreneurial, competitive, client-centered <p>How well does Group Care fit into this organization?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Think of values, norms, management style <p>So far, how have the managers of your organization been involved in the implementation of GC?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Who are these leaders? How do attitudes of different leaders vary? ● What kind of support have they given you? Example? ● What kind of support or actions do you expect from leaders in your organization to help make the implementation of Group Care successful?
<p>Stakeholders</p>	<p>When you need to get something done or to solve a problem, who are your "go-to" people within the organization? Example?</p> <p>Who do we need to get on board for the implementation of GC? Why?</p> <p>Who do you ask if you have questions about GC?</p> <p>Who outside of your organization will help with implementation of GC?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What is their role? What do you expect?
<p>Recommendations - closing</p>	<p>How can GC be made more attractive for you and other facilitators?</p> <p>Do you have any suggestions for the implementation of GC?</p> <p>Thank for participation</p>

APPENDIX 4: Topic guide for Women with GC- experience

Topic	Questions
Start Questions (To be filled in a form)	<p>Age</p> <p>Age of child/week of pregnancy</p> <p>Family situation: Do you already have children? Family situation? Partner?</p> <p>Living Situation (Where? How? Who?)</p> <p>Profession/daytime activity</p> <p>Education</p>
Traditions/rituals	<p>What does your day-to-day life look like?</p> <p>What changed with the pregnancy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● e.g., behaviours, habits, people you meet, special events, traditions, rituals ● Special pregnancy courses? <p>What happens usually during birth and the first hours after birth?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Who is usually present during childbirth? ● What behaviours (changes) are expected? <p>What happens during the first weeks after birth?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What behaviours/events are expected? ● Who will/did you meet? <p>What role do traditional midwives/healers, or birth attendants play during and after your pregnancy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How about alternative medicine?
Utilization of current antenatal/postnatal care	<p>Where do you and (other) pregnant women/young mothers seek health care?</p> <p>How did you learn about the health aspects of pregnancy/delivery and child health?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Examples, what was new to you? ● Where do you get information about family planning?

<p>Beliefs & attitudes</p>	<p>Can you describe your experiences with health care services in general?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Trust towards HCPs, trust in quality of care, hierarchy <p>How are your expenses for health care/ANC covered?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Health insurance? Free? government? Family/partner?
<p>Needs</p>	<p>What is/was important to you during your pregnancy? How do/did you ensure it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What health aspects exactly? ● What other topics (apart from health) is/was important to you during pregnancy? <p>What do you consider to be important for your child during pregnancy? How do/did you ensure it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Health, psycho-social ● What health aspects exactly? <p>In your opinion, what (health) topics are especially relevant for pregnant women/young mothers and their babies in your region/community?</p>
<p>Challenges</p>	<p>Can you think of any challenges that you faced during/after pregnancy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Psychological difficulties, social, health ● Worries <p>Can you think of any challenges that other women/families faced during/after pregnancy?</p> <p>How do you/they cope with these challenges?</p>
<p>Perception of GC</p>	<p>Can you describe how the GC format looked like?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What was the setting? Where? Location and facility? ● How big was the group? Diverse? ● How many facilitators? ● How many sessions? Attendance? ● Online vs. face to face? <p>Can you describe how you experienced GC sessions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How did you feel during the sessions? ● What was the atmosphere like? ● What did you like? What did you dislike? What was missing? <p>Can you describe the relationships with other women and HCPs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What did the contact look like? How do women communicate? ● Trust? How was trust created? <p>In your opinion what are the benefits of GC?</p> <p>What are your concerns about GC?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How do you feel about GC in times of COVID? And about a blended version of GC?

<p>Perception of core elements/format</p>	<p>Can you describe how you feel about receiving individual health assessments in the group space?</p> <p>Can you describe how you feel about participating in self-care activities? (e.g., recording blood pressure, weight) Confident?</p> <p>Can you describe how you feel about sharing your own experiences with a group? And to ask questions? Why did you feel this way?</p> <p>And about listening to others' experiences and questions?</p> <p>What did you think of the interactive activities?</p> <p>What did you think of the materials used?</p> <p>Would you prefer your partner to attend or not attend the sessions? Why?</p> <p>Would you prefer the other women's partners to attend or not attend the sessions? Why?</p>
<p>Topics/format</p>	<p>Which topics were addressed?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Did you learn anything new? What? ● What did you think about the topics? Would you add/reduce any? <p>Which topics would you feel uncomfortable talking about?</p> <p>What did you ask? And what did you not dare to ask or say?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Can you think of any pregnancy related topics that are stigmatized or not talked about openly? ● Should it be addressed in GC? Why/why not? <p>E.g., incontinence, breast feeding in public</p> <p>What would make you feel more comfortable to share your experiences?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● When would you share something personal?
<p>Obstacles</p>	<p>Can you think of obstacles which might/did prevent you or others from attending?</p> <p>Why might women not <i>want</i> to participate in GC?</p> <p>Can you think of any solutions for these obstacles?</p>
<p>Friends and family</p>	<p>What did your friends and family say when you told them that you will attend GC?</p> <p>What did your partner say?</p> <p>Would you advise your friends to attend GC? Why/why not?</p>

Suggestions	Would you attend GC again? Why/Why not? And CPa? How could Group Care be improved? How could attendance be increased? How can women from your community be reached? Any other comments/suggestions?
Closing	Thank for participation and hand debriefing sheet

APPENDIX 5: Topic guide for Women with NO Group Care experience

Topic	Questions
Start Questions	<p>Age</p> <p>Age of child/week of pregnancy</p> <p>Family situation: Do you already have children? Family situation? Partner?</p> <p>Living Situation (Where? How? Who?)</p> <p>Profession/daytime activity</p> <p>Education</p>
Traditions/rituals	<p>What does your day-to-day life look like?</p> <p>What changed with the pregnancy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • e.g., behaviours, habits, people you meet, special events, traditions, rituals <p>What happens during birth and the first hours after birth?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who is usually present during childbirth? <p>What happens during the first weeks after birth?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What behaviours are expected? • Who will/did you meet? Professionals (e.g. kraamzorg) <p>What role do traditional midwives/healers, or birth attendants play during and after your pregnancy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What about alternative medicine?
Utilization of current antenatal/postnatal care	<p>Where do you and (other) pregnant women/young mothers seek health care?</p> <p>How did you learn about the health aspects of pregnancy/delivery and child health?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples, what was new to you? • Where do you get information about family planning?
Beliefs & attitudes	<p>Can you describe your experiences with health care services in general?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust towards HCPs, trust in quality of care, <p>How are your expenses for health care/ANC covered?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health insurance? Free? government? Family/partner?

<p>Personal Experiences with antenatal care</p>	<p>Are you attending/did you ever attend antenatal care?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Can you describe your experience? ● How did you feel during the consultations? ● How was your relationship with the HCP? ● What did you like? ● What could be better? What did you dislike? ● What was missing?
<p>Needs</p>	<p>What is/was important to you during your pregnancy? How do/did you ensure it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What health aspects exactly? ● What other topics (apart from health) is/was important to you during pregnancy? <p>What do you consider to be important for your child during pregnancy? How do/did you ensure it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Health, psycho-social ● What health aspects exactly? <p>In your opinion, what (health) topics are especially relevant for pregnant women/young mothers and their babies in your region/ community?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To what extend does/did the current HC system meet your/your child's needs during pregnancy?
<p>Challenges</p>	<p>Can you think of any challenges that you faced during/after pregnancy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Psychological difficulties, social, health ● Worries <p>Can you think of any challenges that other women/families faced during/after pregnancy?</p> <p>How do you/they cope with these challenges?</p>

Vignette

Anne, a woman from a [local setting] is 12 weeks pregnant with her first child. During her first antenatal consultation, the midwife invited Anne to join group care for pregnant women. Group care is a different way to deliver antenatal care. In group care 8-12 women meet 9 times for 2 hours throughout their pregnancy and 1 time after giving birth. During those meetings, which are facilitated by 1 or 2 HCPs, the women's and their babies' health is assessed and many questions about pregnancy and parenting are discussed in the group.

Today, is the first group care appointment. Anne arrives at the health care centre and walks to a separate room where she meets the facilitators, Jane who is a midwife and Lisa, a maternity assistant. They welcome Anne and introduce her to a few other women who already arrived. A few chairs form a circle and Anne takes a seat on one of them and she starts talking to the woman who sits next to her while waiting until everyone arrives.

A few more women arrive and Jane announces that they are complete now. 12 pregnant women are in the room now and they all take a seat in the circle. Jane explains how GC works: Throughout all antenatal meetings, the same health care professional will be there, namely Jane and Lisa. Also, the same women will attend and no one else will join at a later stage. Jane explains that Lisa will teach the women how to take some health measurements and note them. The women are invited to have a chat with each other during these assessments. Meanwhile, the women will join Jane one by one in the back where the health of mother and baby will be checked individually. Jane tells the women that starting from the next session, the women can begin with taking some health assessments themselves as soon as they arrive.

Lisa stays with Anne and the other women and she shows them how to measure their own blood pressure and she explains why this is so important. With the help of Lisa, Anne measures her blood pressure and she notes it in her record book. During the following appointments, Anne and the other women will be able to take this measurement by themselves and they will be able to monitor their records throughout the pregnancy. In this way, the women learn to recognize health complications themselves, which makes Anne feel empowered. From now on, she understands much better what is going on.

After Anne's weight and blood pressure was checked, Jane invites Anne to join her in the back of the room. Jane asks Anne to lay down on a mat and listens to the baby's heartbeat and palpate Anne's belly. Anne is very curious and wants to know what Jane feels with her hands. In response to Anne's questions Jane explains what her hands are feeling. This part of the room is somewhat more private as a room divider separates it from the women's circle. The assessment doesn't take long and now Anne joins the other women back in the circle.

After about 30 minutes all health assessments are done and Lisa invites everyone to join the circle. Jane starts with asking about the expectations of the women from this group care sessions, and which topics the women really want to discuss today. A few women mention that they would like to know more about what really is good for your health during pregnancy and what is just a myth. Jane begins the conversation by asking: "What do you think is important during pregnancy with regards to your own health?". A few women mention avoidance of alcohol consumption, taking vitamins, stress, and blood pressure, etc. In this way a discussion begins, and everyone shares their thoughts and questions. Anne is surprised to learn about the severe consequences of high blood pressure during pregnancy. She also did not know that drinking alcohol can increase her blood pressure.

After the talk about health behaviours during pregnancy, it's time for a break. During the break the women talk, drink tea and they have some snacks that are provided until Lisa informs them that it is time to continue.

After the break new topics are discussed and Anne gets a better understanding of what to expect from the following group care sessions. Jane explained that they will address more 'typical' topics as they did today, but that pregnancy-related issues that are usually overlooked also will be addressed, such as mental health challenges.

About two hours after Anne arrived, this first Group Care session ends.

<p>General impression of GC</p>	<p>What do you think about this form of care?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What do you like/dislike? <p>In your opinion what are the benefits of GC?</p> <p>What are your concerns about this form of care?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How do you feel about GC in times of COVID? And about a blended version of GC?
<p>Perception of core elements</p>	<p>How would you feel about receiving individual health assessments in the group space?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fetal heartbeat, position of baby, blood sample <p>How would you feel about participating in self-care activities? (e.g., recording blood pressure)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Do you think that you would be capable? (why not?) <p>How would you feel about sharing your own experiences in a group? And about listening to others' experiences and questions?</p> <p>How would you feel about asking questions in the group sessions?</p>
<p>Topics/format</p>	<p>What topics would you like to address in the group sessions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What questions would you like to ask? ● What would you like to learn about? <p>Which topics would you feel uncomfortable talking about?</p> <p>Can you think of any pregnancy related topics that are stigmatized or not talked about openly?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Should it be addressed in GC? ● E.g., Incontinence, breast feeding in public <p>Would you prefer your partner to attend or not attend the sessions? Why?</p> <p>Would you prefer the other women's partners to attend or not attend the sessions? Why?</p> <p>What would make you feel more comfortable to share your experiences?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● When would you share something personal?
<p>Obstacles</p>	<p>Can you think of obstacles which might prevent you (or others) from attending?</p> <p>Can you think of any reasons why women might not want to participate in GC?</p> <p>Can you think of any solutions for these obstacles?</p>

Friends and family	<p>What would your friends and family say if you told them that you will attend GC?</p> <p>What would your partner say?</p>
Suggestions	<p>Would you attend GC? Why/why not?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What would make GC more attractive for you? When would you attend? <p>Do you have ideas on how we could reach other women?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How can we make participation more attractive? ● When would women attend? <p>Would you like to add anything?</p>
Closing	<p>Thank for participation and hand debriefing sheet</p>

APPENDIX 6: Topic guide for partner organisations from your setting – antenatal Group Care

- Estimated time: 30-40minutes
- introduction about the research, and more specific about the setting

Vignette - video

Topic	Questions
Start Questions 3A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● By who/which organization are you employed? ● What is your title within your organization? ● What are your main responsibilities? (before implementation of GC) ● What's your professional background?
Vulnerable pregnant women	Can you describe the needs of (vulnerable) pregnant women in your region?
	Vignette
Personal view and knowledge about GC by Health Care Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What's your first impression of Group Care after hearing this story? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● advantages/disadvantages? Compared to current antenatal care? ● what do you know about the evidence based of GC? ● Can you tell me what you know about experiences with group care? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Other organizations? ● Participants?
GC within organization: WHY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How will group care affect your organization? ● How do you think GC can meet the needs of the pregnant women in your organization? ● Can you think of any regulations that might affect the implementation of GC? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● local/state/national? ● reimbursement? ... ● What aspects of the general health care system in your country will influence the implementation of GC in that setting? (Facilitate or impede?) ● Is Group Care seen as a priority in your organization? Can you give some examples that reflect this? (3D.c) ● How do you prioritize the implementation of GC in that setting? Can you also give some examples? (3C)

<p>GC within organization: Decision process</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How is your organization involved in the implementation of Group Care? (if applicable) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What is your role within this implementation project? ● How were you/your organization involved in the decision process? ● Why do you consider your organization important to be involved in the implementation and organization of GC? ● Can you tell me how you/your organization could support the implementation/organization?
<p>GC within organization: HOW</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Can you describe how Group Care will be integrated into the daily work (in your organization)? ● What is your plan for getting the word out about Group Care? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How will you inform people about the existence of group care? ● How will you recruit women for attending GC? (if applicable) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>What materials/modes/venues do you plan to use? For example e-bulletin boards, emails, brochures?</i> ● <i>What process do you plan to use to communicate? For example, going to staff meetings, talking to people informally?</i> ● <i>reaching the women / motivating to attend/ ...</i>
<p>Key stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Who are other key influential individuals to get on board with this implementation of Group Care? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To encourage individuals to use the intervention? ● To help with implementation?
<p>Closing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What would make GC more attractive for you as a partner in the implementation of GC? ● Do you have any other suggestions for the implementation of GC? ● Thank for participation

APPENDIX 7: Vignette

Anne, a woman from X is 12 weeks pregnant with her first child. During her first antenatal consultation, the midwife invited Anne to join group care for pregnant women. Group care is a different way to deliver antenatal care. In group care 8-12 women meet 9 times for 2 hours throughout their pregnancy and 1 time after giving birth. During those meetings, which are facilitated by 1 or 2 HCPs, the women's and their babies' health is assessed and many questions about pregnancy and parenting are discussed in the group.

Today, is the first group care appointment. Anne arrives at the health care centre and walks to a separate room where she meets the facilitators, Jane who is a midwife and Lisa, a maternity assistant. They welcome Anne and introduce her to a few other women who already arrived. A few chairs form a circle and Anne takes a seat on one of them and she starts talking to the woman who sits next to her while waiting until everyone arrives.

A few more women arrive and Jane announces that they are complete now. 12 pregnant women are in the room now and they all take a seat in the circle. Jane explains how GC works: Throughout all antenatal meetings, the same health care professional will be there, namely Jane and Lisa. Also, the same women will attend and no one else will join at a later stage. Jane explains that Lisa will teach the women how to take some health measurements and note them. The women are invited to have a chat with each other during these assessments. Meanwhile, the women will join Jane one by one in the back where the health of mother and baby will be checked individually. Jane tells the women that starting from the next session, the women can begin with taking some health assessments themselves as soon as they arrive.

Lisa stays with Anne and the other women and she shows them how to measure their own blood pressure and she explains why this is so important. With the help of Lisa, Anne measures her blood pressure and she notes it in her record book. During the following appointments, Anne and the other women will be able to take this measurement by themselves and they will be able to monitor their records throughout the pregnancy. In this way, the women learn to recognize health complications themselves, which makes Anne feel empowered. From now on, she understands much better what is going on.

After Anne's weight and blood pressure was checked, Jane invites Anne to join her in the back of the room. Jane asks Anne to lay down on a mat and listens to the baby's heartbeat and palpate Anne's belly. Anne is very curious and wants to know what Jane feels with her hands. In response to Anne's questions Jane explains what her hands are feeling. This part of the room is somewhat more private as a room divider separates it from the women's circle. The assessment doesn't take long and now Anne joins the other women back in the circle.

After about 30 minutes all health assessments are done and Lisa invites everyone to join the circle. Jane starts with asking about the expectations of the women from this group care sessions, and which topics the women really want to discuss today. A few women mention that they would like to know more about what really is good for your health during pregnancy and what is just a myth. Jane begins the conversation by asking: "What do you think is important during pregnancy with regards to your own health?". A few women mention avoidance of alcohol consumption, tak-

ing vitamins, stress, and blood pressure, etc. In this way a discussion begins, and everyone shares their thoughts and questions. Anne is surprised to learn about the severe consequences of high blood pressure during pregnancy. She also did not know that drinking alcohol can increase her blood pressure.

After the talk about health behaviours during pregnancy, it's time for a break. During the break the women talk, drink tea and they have some snacks that are provided until Lisa informs them that it is time to continue.

After the break new topics are discussed and Anne gets a better understanding of what to expect from the following group care sessions. Jane explained that they will address more 'typical' topics as they did today, but that pregnancy-related issues that are usually overlooked also will be addressed, such as mental health challenges.

About two hours after Anne arrived, this first Group Care session ends.

APPENDIX 8: Contact summary form

Name of researcher: Date:

Type of contact:
(function) (place)

1. Why was this participant interviewed? And what is his/her role in the implementation of GC?
2. What were the main issues or themes that struck you in this contact?
3. Summarize the information you got (or failed to get) on each of the target questions!

Local needs:

Implementation Barriers:

Implementation Facilitators:

Perception of GC:

4. Anything else that struck you as important/surprising/interesting?
5. What new (or remaining) questions need to be further investigated in this setting? And how do the research tools need to adapted for this?